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Assessing Intra-Site Variability of Compaction Magnitudes and Carbon Emissions in an Oil Palm Plantation on the Drained Tropical Peatland

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Abstract

Change of land use from peat secondary forest (SF) to oil palm plantation (OP) involves several specific practices that may contribute to soil property heterogeneity. Specifically, artificial compaction as marked by increased bulk density value was assessed in relation to repeating microsities identified in standard plantation design, and defined as harvesting path 'HP', under canopy 'UC', frond pile 'FP', and far from tree 'FF'. Along with soil sampling at 25 cm depth, carbon emissions were measured within OP microsities using dynamic closed-chambers. The samples were collected at three different oil palm ages, namely A1 (15 years, 1st generation), A2 (9 years, 2nd generation), and A3 (2 years, second generation and previously burned) between November 2015 and May 2016. Compaction, as indicated by bulk density values, had been comparable among microsities but differed among OP ages. This suggests that compaction source within OP was solely due to period of drainage and the previous fire event. Meanwhile, CO₂ emission was positively correlated with water proxies and pH, signifying the important of rainfall to dilute soil pH. Here we suggest that this leads to an increase in the solubility of organic matter and subsequently, an increase the availability of labile C to microbes, thus enhancing respiration and CO₂ production. Despite absence of evidence that directly indicated effect of compaction, microsities emission variation was clear and employed to determine Surface Area Correction (SAC) for land use emission factor (EF) calculation. The value retrieved for EF using SAC was between the default value proposed by IPCC (2010) and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) (2014). The SAC was also applied to estimate EF reduction by limiting the number of palms per hectare and by converting FP microsities into HP and FF, which resulted in up to 11% of carbon reduction. Hence, identification of microsities emission variability offers data for complementary strategies in managing OP across tropical peatlands.

Keywords: Agriculture management, Bulk density, Compaction, Carbon emission, Microsities, Oil palm ages

INTRODUCTION

Peatland is vital ecologically and through their function in terrestrial carbon sequestration. As such, this fragile ecosystem can mitigate adverse climate change (Lal, 2004). The global carbon pool under this ecosystem amounts to 550 Gt (Wetlands International) of which approximately 247,778 km² or 68.5 Gt is in Southeast Asia (Page *et al.*, 2011). This includes about 9.1 Gt in Malaysia. However, peatland areas have been massively exploited resulting in deforestation, drainage, and burning. One primary reason is oil palm (OP) plantation establishment. As a result, carbon loss due to conversion from peatland to OP, resulted in approximately 13.3 Mt yr⁻¹ carbon loss from 666,038 hectares (in year 2009) of OP areas for Malaysia (Carlson *et al.*, 2015). In the past decades, the design of OP plantation layout has turned into an important industry topic with the aim of maximising yield and productivity (Mutert *et al.*, 1999). While, the plantation monoculture resulting from conversion of forest ecosystem to plantation adversely affect species richness, subsequent maturation of plantations can also provide unwitting areas of rehabilitation through unwedded microsities within OP (Luskin & Potts, 2011) or frond piling (Henson *et al.*, 2012). Each microsite has

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distinct characteristics depending on standard planting density and management practices. These attributes are hypothesised to affect site-specific peat property heterogeneity.

The initial land clearance and construction of water canals to control water table level (Hooijer *et al.*, 2012; Ritzema *et al.*, 2014) and land preparation for planting oil palm seedling (Mutert *et al.*, 1999) via the use of heavy machinery, all contribute to potential peat property heterogeneity, especially in relation to compaction of soil and resulting bulk density. In addition to this, the continuously occurring management practices specific to each microsites (e.g. fertiliser and liming application; Wösten *et al.*, 1997), as well as harvesting of FFB or frond piling (Yahya *et al.*, 2011) throughout an entire palm cycle have the potential to compound this intra-site variation. Indirectly, carbon emission may also be affected by these attributes. In general, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions heavily rely on micro-topography, hydro-period, biophysical or above ground plant pool (Jauhiainen *et al.*, 2014; Miao *et al.*, 2013; Moore & Dalva, 1997). However, information on peat bulk density and other peat physico-chemical characteristics across microsite and temporal scales in relation to potential variability in artificial compaction in tropical peat soils is unavailable. In a compaction study of OP at Bernam Series soil a mineral type soil, Yahya *et al.*, (2011) discovered that bulk density and total porosity in HP increased by 10.5% and reduced by 5%, respectively, when compared to FP area after six years of oil palm cultivation. Nevertheless, these outcomes cannot be applied in tropical peatland mainly because peat lacks clay content (Alakukku, 1996).

While partitioning the heterotrophic and autotrophic contributions of soil respiration (SR) by roots availability has been studied extensively (i.e. Dariah *et al.*, 2014; Jauhiainen *et al.*, 2012; Lim & Ahmed, 2014; Matysek *et al.*, 2018)., these studies do not capture the heterogeneity within these zones, nor are the contribution of these areas accounted for in terms of up-scaled emissions estimated for entire plantations. The implication for informed policy making is significant; In 2011, the US EPA (EPA, 2014) undertook peer reviews from several experts in tropical peat research to discuss the usage of a default OP on peat emissions factor (EF) value. While this resulted in a determination of 95 t CO_{2-eq} ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, this remains largely inflated compared to the 40 t CO_{2-eq} ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ proposed by IPCC 2007. Thus, in order to address uncertainties in calculating the EF of drained OP on tropical peatland, while much of this ambiguity lies in emissions within the first 5 years of conversion, varied peat generation and intra-site heterogeneity also requires full accounting.

Given the information gaps, the objectives of this study are as follows: (1) to quantify peat physical properties, as well as CO₂ and CH₄ emissions, at varied OP ages within described microsites, and (2) to correlate between peat physical properties and carbon emission (3) To use EFs from specific microsites to proportionally upscale (by representative area) total emissions per hectare of OP plantation. This study hypothesised that peat artificial compaction marked by bulk density and other selected physiochemical properties within microsites are affected by oil palm management as defined by specific microsite type. This influences the variation of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions from peat surface.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling location and microsites identification

The plantation identified was established in 1970's overlies with a small area of remnant primary forest preserved at the adjacent Kuala Langat South Forest Reserve and surrounds the KLIA airport. This plantation was chosen as it is a well-established field site, providing contextual data and site information for the project (Adeolu *et al.*, 2015; Marshall *et al.*, 2018; Matysek *et al.*, 2018; Waldron *et al.*, 2019). Sites were chosen to represent differing plantation age groups, however specific sites within plantation age blocks were identified randomly. Site A1 established 15 years ago (1st generation), site A2, 34 years ago (9 year old palm, second generation), and site A3 also 34 years ago (2 year old palms, 3rd generation after 9 year old palms burnt) (a cycle OP is 25 years; Zulkifli *et al.*, 2010). Sampling campaign was carried out between wet and dry seasons in November 2015 and June 2016. Although, the number of rain days observed during dry season (30 days) exceeded that of the wet season (20 days), the rainfall average was much lower (i.e. dry

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season; 4.9 mm/day, and wet season; 15.4 mm/day). Subsequently, water table levels had high ranges that fluctuated between -21.6 cm and -74.3 cm (Table 1). However, this was due to sampling during a El Nino event which was among the strongest (*Malaysian Meteorological Department (MMD) Annual Report, 2016*). In contrast, previous data from this site shows much greater drainage occurs with water table depths of -70 to -120 cm during dry weather condition of June and August 2014 (*Matysek et al., 2018*).

Table 1 Mean \pm standard error (n =24) of water table level (WTL) at KLIA, Sepang oil palm plantation during wet and dry seasons.

Season	Wet			Dry		
	A1	A2	A3	A1	A2	A3
Water table level (cm)	-36.9 \pm 1.3	-62.3 \pm 3.9	-38.0 \pm 2.7	-21.6 \pm 4.6	-58.7 \pm 2.6	-74.3 \pm 3.1

In this study, peat thickness at sites were 101.5 \pm 3.5cm, 84.2 \pm 2.1cm, and 82.5 \pm 2.8 cm at A1, A2, and A3 sites, which is considered as shallow thick peat in accordance with the Peninsular Malaysia peat classification (*Hajon et al., 2018*). Details of these microsites Harvesting Path (HP), Under Canopy (UC), Frond Pile (FP) and Far From palm (FF) are illustrated in Figure 1 and described in Table 2. Excluding UC microsite (palm centre), all the other microsites (e.g. HP, FP, and FF) and associated samplings were placed more than 3.0 m from the palm trunks based on the distance of potential heterotrophic respiration, as suggested by *Dariah et al. (2014)*. A total of 72 soil and gas samples were gathered from two sampling seasons, three OP ages, and four microsites with three replications.

Figure 1 Oil palm plantation that classified into different microsites namely Harvesting Path (HP), Under Canopy (UC), Frond Piles (FP) and Far from Palm (FP).

Table 2 The main characteristics of microsites within oil palm plantation observed in this study.

Microsites	Main characteristic	References
Harvesting path (HP)	Exposed directly to sunlight and rainfall, may be shaded by palm fronds after five years old. The main path for oil palm plantation activities. May serve as wildlife corridor due to presence of animal tracks (see Appendix A). Compaction intensity was expected to be the highest among others.	Lestariningsih <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Shestak & Busse, 2005; Comeau <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Mutert <i>et al.</i> , 1999; Yahya <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Under Canopy (UC)	Almost free from sunlight and rainfall due to shed from palm canopy. Peat surface is mainly dominated by underground palm roots and a focused area for fertiliser and liming application. The compaction intensity is dominated by palm roots distribution and previously during hole in one compaction for planting seedling.	Comeau <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Mutert <i>et al.</i> , 1999; Yahya <i>et al.</i> , 2011;
Frond Pile (FP)	During early stage of establishment, this microsite is exposed directly to sunlight and rainfall, but expected to be covered as a result from the plantation management (pruned fronds). The compaction effort is influenced by the weight of freshly pruned	Lestariningsih <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Yahya <i>et al.</i> , 2011

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fronds and timely decayed fronds.

Far from Palm (FF)	A passive microsite, whereby soil surface in this microsite is covered by aboveground pioneer species. Nearby feeder drains. Peat compaction may occur due to roots distribution and weight of decayed plant biomass.	Ariyanti <i>et al.</i> , 2016 and by field observation.
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Peat depth and physicochemical sampling

Peat thickness was determined by using Russian peat auger with 50.0 cm length (Eijkelkamp Soil and Water, Netherlands). Concurrently, peat samples were collected at 25.0 cm depth from after depth measurement. Peat bulk density samples were collected by using fabricated soil core with 173.18 cm³ volume. Prior to sampling, the peat was dug to make a soil pit of 50.0 cm depth. Peat bulk density sample was collected on the wall of the pit to minimise vertical compaction (Hooijer *et al.*, 2012). Next, the core was carefully pushed horizontally onto the wall of the pit that displayed minimal amount of semi-decomposed woody materials. The core penetration was assisted by cutting off coarse fragments or palm root with a sharp knife along the cutting edge of the sampler. When the sampler was full, peat around the sampler was cut and carefully taken out from the pit. After that, the sample was trimmed based on the sampler size. In order to hinder evaporation from the fresh peat sample, the sampler was tightly closed with a cap before it was transferred to the laboratory.

Peat physicochemical analysis

On return to the lab, the dry bulk density was analysed following the core method presented by Alshammary *et al.* (2018). Loss on ignition was determined from a small portion of composite oven-dried peat (5.0 g) by complete combustion using the muffle furnace at 550°C for 12 hours following the method prescribed in Marwanto *et al.* (2019). As mentioned in after (Blake, 1958), the value of particle density can be obtained using pycnometer or specific gravity flask. Subsequently, calculation of total porosity was based on peat particle density value obtained. Water filled pore space was calculated using gravitational moisture content based on dry weight and volume of moisture content parameters (Tonks *et al.*, 2017). The composite dry samples from soil core were further crushed by mortar and pestle and passed through 2.0 mm sieve for chemical properties determination (Sakata *et al.*, 2015). Peat pH value was determined using benchtop pH meter model (Sartorius pHBasic, Germany) by placing 5.0 g of dried and sieved peat sample with 12.5 ml deionised water (soil-water ratio of 1:2.5).

Gas sampling using dynamic closed-chamber method

Excluding UC microsite (palm centre), all the other microsites and associated chambers were placed more than 3.0 m from the palm trunks based on the distance of potential HR, as suggested by Dariah *et al.*, (2014). Gas emissions sampling was performed from morning until mid-afternoon (1000-1400 hr). Carbon emission was captured by using the dynamic closed-chamber method by following the gas sampling protocols prescribed in GRACEnet project (Parkin & Venterea, 2010) involving microsites. Four square-shaped closed-chambers with open-ended base and sharp edges were fabricated using clear acrylic material measuring 20.0 cm (width) x 20.0 cm (height) x 20.0 cm (length). Next, they were wrapped with aluminium foil to minimise the effect of temperature variance in the chamber. Two sampling ports plugged with rubber septum were fitted on top of the chamber for gas sampling and thermometer installation. Additionally, a battery-operated fan was attached inside the chamber to allow dynamic air flow (Zerva, 2004). Prior to chamber placement, the existing plant debris on the soil surface was removed as carefully as possible using soft brush until the surface peat was discovered. As for the FF microsite, the aboveground plant was removed two weeks prior to gas sampling. Removal of plant debris was required to homogenise peat surface among the microsites and to prevent leakage on the chamber bottom edge due to uneven placement caused by thick plant biomass resembling a mat. In this study, anchor or soil collar for chamber was neglected because the edge of the chamber was cut with a sharp knife and pushed vertically for lateral diffusion into the soil to the depth of 3.0 cm to avoid gas leakage (Melling *et al.*, 2005). Use of anchor at these sites was

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unsuitable as most of the sites are prone to flooding and accumulation of water inside collar was expected. Upon chamber placement, 20.0 mL gas sample was extracted from the chamber from T₀ to T₅ (1, 3, 6, 9, and 12 minutes) time interval by using a polypropylene syringe equipped with a three-way stopcock. The extracted gas was transferred into a 20.0 mL glass vial that had been vacuumed earlier and stored in a box at room temperature (30 °C) prior to gas analysis using gas chromatography (GC).

Gas concentration analysis and calculation

Gas samples were analysed using GC (Agilent model 7890A) equipped with thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and flame ionisation detector (FID) to determine CO₂ and CH₄, respectively. The GC was calibrated by using standard mixed gases that consisted of 1.0 ppm of CH₄, 350.0 ppm of CO₂, and 50.0 ppm of N₂O, until it hit 90% of sensitivity value. Gas concentration in ppm was calculated by using ideal gas law, as given in Eq. (1):

$$PV = nRT \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where: P = Atmospheric pressure (101,325 pa); V = Volume of headspace (m³); n = Number of moles (mol); R = Universal Gas Constant law (8.314J. K⁻¹mol⁻¹) and T = Temperature in kelvin (K) with conversion number of 1 mol of gas to gram, CO₂ = 44.01 g and CH₄ = 16.02 g, respectively.

The increase or decrease in the chamber concentration over time (hour, h⁻¹) by chamber volume (L) from peat surface area covered (m²) was fitted into LR with at least three sampling points, including T₀ point. The slope from LR denotes the rate of CO₂ or CH₄ emission (+ value) / uptake (-value) and presented in, mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ or µg CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹. Any concentration point that observed outlier in LR graph due to sampling time error was omitted from the calculation (retain at least three points of gas concentration). Another prerequisite for LR is that the regression line must exceed R²=0.60. The estimation of AR was obtained by subtracting HR rate from the total soil respiration rate (SR) (Melling *et al.*, 2013).

Surface Area Correction (SAC)

The proposed method of SAC was calculated based on common planting density of OP across tropical peatland in triangular planting (Figure 2) in accordance to 160 palms per hectare, which has been commonly exercised on tropical peatland. The steps to calculate SAC are as follows: First, calculate the area covered by UC using the area of the circle with radius (R_{op}) value of 3.0 m that represents effective SR based on oil palm root, as proposed by Dariah *et al.*, (2014). The value of UC was 28.28 m² per palm. Next, calculate the FP value by assuming that the fronds piles were located side-by-side to the palm. Assuming FP microsite was rectangular in shape and subtracted by the UC area and given the length of hypotenuse for planting density was 8.5 m and the length of one side was half of UC that of 1.5 m, the other side can be calculated by using Pythagorean Theorem. After that, using UC and FP values, calculations of HP and FF were made by assuming that both microsites shared similar area of rectangular shape. Therefore, the value of HP was calculated by deducting 10,000 m² or 1.0 hectare from UC and FP values and later, divided by two. Hence, the proportion of microsites area were 0.224, 0.452, 0.1, and 0.224 for HP, UC, FP, and FF, respectively, which led to 1.0 or 100% (Table 3).

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Figure 2 Typical planting density of oil palm plantation on tropical peatland in equilateral triangle planting density of 8.5 m x 8.5 m x 8.5 m.

Table 3 Calculation of palm per microsite area based on oil palm planting density on tropical peat land that of 160 palms per hectare.

Microsites	Area Calculation (m ²)	Surface Area Correction Factor
Harvesting Path (HP)	$[10,000 \text{ m}^2 - 160 (\text{UC} + \text{FP})] / 2$	0.224
Under Canopy (UC)	$\pi 3^2$; Rop = 3.0 m	0.452
Fronde Pile (FP)	$\text{UC} - 2 (1.5 \times 7.36) \text{ m}$	0.100
Far from Palm (FF)	HP = FF	0.224
	Total	1.000

Statistical analyses

Prior to ANOVA, assumptions of data normality and equality of variance were checked by using Ryan-Joiner's method (similar to Shapiro-Wilk method) and Levene's method (Brown & Forsythe, 1974; Shapiro & Wilk, 2006; Yap & Sim, 2011). The effects of spatiotemporal variation (microsites and OP ages) on physicochemical properties and carbon emission had been assessed by employed the general linear model (GLM). Factors with significant difference at $p < 0.05$ reflect further analysis and separation via Tukey's post-hoc analysis (Tukey, 1949) at 95% confidence level. The correlation between peat properties and carbon emission in the form of CO₂ and CH₄ was tested using Pearson's correlation coefficient method with two-tailed at 0.05 probability level. All statistical analyses were performed using MINITAB17[®] statistical software package, while the graphs were plotted using Sigma Plot version 12.5 software.

RESULTS

Peat physicochemical properties

The analysis outcomes pertaining to effects of two factors of temporal (OP ages) and spatial (microsites) variation on peat properties are tabulated in Table 4, while the mean values for the peat parameters are presented in Table 5. Dry bulk density differed between OP ages ($p = 0.027$) but not microsites ($p = 0.236$). The highest bulk density was measured at A3, followed by A2 and A1 with mean values of 0.188 g cm⁻³, 0.184 g cm⁻³, and 0.155 g cm⁻³, respectively. Similarly, loss on ignition exhibited variation between plantation ages ($p = 0.001$). The lowest loss on ignition was discovered at A2, followed by A3 and A1 with mean values of 87.59%, 92.7%, and 94.89%, respectively. Meanwhile, the pH value in this study was influenced by microsite variation ($p = 0.024$). The highest pH value was observed at UC, followed by FF, FP, and HP with mean values of 3.75 ± 0.12 , 3.63 ± 0.09 , 3.51 ± 0.08 , and 3.39 ± 0.05 , respectively. It was noted that specific gravity, total porosity, volumetric water content, gravimetric water content, and water-filled pore space differed neither between plantation ages nor microsites with mean values of 1.699 ± 0.048 g cm⁻³, $89.04 \pm 0.46\%$, $41.8 \pm 3.1\%$, $266.3 \pm 25\%$, $46.57 \pm 3.34\%$, and 3.57 ± 0.05 , respectively.

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Table 4 General Linear Model (GLM) analysis for spatial (Micro = microsities) and temporal (Age = oil palm plantation ages) variations factors for peat properties in this study. The bolded F-values with *, ** and *** are significant at 0.05, 0.01 and ≤ 0.001 , respectively.

Source	df	Peat properties ANOVA (F-value)							
		Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Loss on ignition (%)	Specific gravity (g cm ⁻³)	Total porosity (%)	Volumetric water content (%)	Gravimetric water content (%)	Water-filled pores space (%)	pH value (1:2.5) (Peat:water)
Age	2	3.84*	8.43***	2.45	1.29	1.19	0.84	1.24	0.09
Micro	3	1.45	0.66	0.05	0.65	0.76	0.51	0.88	3.38*
Age x micro	2	0.89	0.45	0.23	0.56	0.30	0.24	0.34	1.91

Table 5 Peat physicochemical properties at 25.0 cm depth. The values presented are mean \pm standard error (n = 6).

Age	Microsite	Peat properties							
		Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Loss on ignition (%)	Specific gravity (g cm ⁻³)	Total porosity (%)	Volumetric water content (%)	Gravimetric water content (%)	Water-filled pore space (%)	pH value (1:2.5) (Peat:water)
A1	HP	0.15 \pm 0.02	94.59 \pm 0.97	1.59 \pm 0.11	90.53 \pm 1.24	37.57 \pm 7.94	291.4 \pm 82.3	41.24 \pm 4.60	3.44 \pm 0.07
	UC	0.16 \pm 0.01	91.79 \pm 3.23	1.60 \pm 0.07	89.85 \pm 0.98	30.68 \pm 8.79	193.3 \pm 55.2	34.50 \pm 10.1	3.94 \pm 0.28
	FP	0.16 \pm 0.01	90.97 \pm 4.19	1.55 \pm 0.03	89.93 \pm 0.98	45.10 \pm 10.1	293.1 \pm 66.3	50.30 \pm 11.4	3.39 \pm 0.10
	FF	0.16 \pm 0.01	93.42 \pm 1.43	1.58 \pm 0.08	90.07 \pm 0.82	36.50 \pm 9.51	239.8 \pm 67.6	40.40 \pm 10.4	3.46 \pm 0.09
A2	HP	0.17 \pm 0.02	90.66 \pm 1.59	1.58 \pm 0.20	88.63 \pm 1.60	48.65 \pm 6.80	316.3 \pm 72.6	54.48 \pm 6.89	3.42 \pm 0.12
	UC	0.17 \pm 0.01	84.53 \pm 3.71	1.74 \pm 0.15	90.14 \pm 0.91	23.95 \pm 4.43	153.7 \pm 36.4	26.39 \pm 4.77	3.76 \pm 0.21
	FP	0.21 \pm 0.02	88.40 \pm 2.78	1.76 \pm 0.12	87.82 \pm 1.83	40.78 \pm 7.73	227.9 \pm 59.3	45.79 \pm 8.27	3.59 \pm 0.13
	FF	0.19 \pm 0.01	86.75 \pm 3.07	1.62 \pm 0.10	88.10 \pm 1.06	43.57 \pm 9.52	229.7 \pm 51.4	49.40 \pm 10.7	3.48 \pm 0.05
A3	HP	0.20 \pm 0.03	94.98 \pm 1.48	1.94 \pm 0.26	88.52 \pm 2.30	53.60 \pm 16.4	347.0 \pm 148.0	59.10 \pm 17.1	3.31 \pm 0.08
	UC	0.12 \pm 0.02	95.81 \pm 0.70	1.75 \pm 0.29	88.27 \pm 2.28	47.80 \pm 17.5	339.0 \pm 152.0	52.40 \pm 18.3	3.57 \pm 0.12
	FP	0.22 \pm 0.03	94.23 \pm 2.31	1.86 \pm 0.22	86.04 \pm 2.60	49.90 \pm 13.5	261.0 \pm 106.0	57.30 \pm 14.5	3.56 \pm 0.16
	FF	0.16 \pm 0.02	93.88 \pm 2.16	1.81 \pm 0.27	90.63 \pm 1.56	43.50 \pm 13.1	304.0 \pm 105.0	47.50 \pm 13.9	3.95 \pm 0.20

Carbon emissions from oil palm plantation

Emission of CO₂ at A1, A2, and A3 within microsities ranged from 519 to 1393 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹, 879 to 1421 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹, and 717 to 1018 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹, respectively. No effect of CO₂ emission was noted on two-factor interaction with the total CO₂ emission cumulative of 991 \pm 63 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ ($p = 0.703$). Nevertheless, variance was noted between microsities (Figure 3; $p = 0.018$). The greatest CO₂ emission was observed at UC microsite and differed to FP microsite ($p = 0.026$) with mean values of 1278 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ and 763 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹, respectively. Emission of CO₂ from microsities HP and FF were comparable with other microsities with mean values 1068 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ and 855 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹, respectively. Meanwhile, emissions of CH₄ at A1, A2, and A3 within OP ages ranged from 3.9 to 218 μ g CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹, 50 to 246 μ g CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹, and 94 to 215 μ g CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹, respectively. However, CH₄ emission had no effect on spatiotemporal variation with mean value of 172 \pm 27 μ g CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹ ($p = 0.275$).

Figure 3 CO₂ emission from microsities in oil palm plantation, Sepang, South Selangor. The error bars indicate standard error of means. The different letters signify significant variances between microsities. The means were separated using Tukey's HSD post-hoc test ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Relationship between carbon emissions and physical properties

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Pearson's correlation coefficient was performed to determine the correlation between carbon emission and peat physical properties (Table 6). The results showed that CO₂ emission was positively correlated with volumetric water content ($p = 0.018$), gravimetric water content ($p = 0.020$), water-filled pore space ($p = 0.017$), and pH value ($p < 0.001$), whereas CH₄ emission was positively correlated with pH value ($p < 0.001$).

Table 6 Values represent Pearson's correlation coefficient r , between carbon emissions and peat physical properties ($n = 72$). The bolded r values with *, ** and *** are significant at 0.05, 0.01 and ≤ 0.001 , respectively.

Carbon emission	Peat physical properties with Pearson's correlation coefficient (r)							
	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Loss of ignition (%)	Specific gravity (g cm ⁻³)	Total porosity (%)	Volumetric water content (%)	Gravimetric water content (%)	Water-filled pore space (%)	pH value
CO ₂	-0.067	-0.135	0.108	0.130	0.346**	0.321**	0.350**	0.473***
CH ₄	-0.158	-0.135	0.107	0.230	0.184	0.178	0.179	0.642***

DISCUSSION

Compaction within microsites in matured oil palm plantation

A total of 72 peat samples were assessed to identify the effects of spatiotemporal factors on peat physical properties (Table 4). As mentioned, dry bulk density value is an integral variable that determines the intensity of soil compaction. The hypothesis in this study states that bulk density changes based on plantation management intensity (microsites). This hypothesis is rejected as bulk density is influenced by plantation ages, wherein A3 displayed the highest bulk density. Thus, the assumption that artificial compaction is varied between microsites that marked by bulk density remains uncertain. Results also in disagreement with Yahya *et al.* (2011) which mentioned the bulk density are varied between microsites, and the discrepancy may due to Bernam Series of clay textual as compared to peat which nearly 99.0% of organic matter (Huat *et al.*, 2011). Nevertheless, the change in bulk density between plantation ages is probably due to plantation establishment, which is reflected by drainage period (Hooijer *et al.*, 2012). This suggests that bulk density increases due to the wide range and controlled water table level for a long period (Jauhainen *et al.*, 2012), hence affecting peat shrinkage (Price, 2003) as a result of distinct wet and dry regimes. Subsequently, increased compression in the oxic peat horizon leads to subsidence, owing to oxidation (Price & Schlotzhauer, 1999; Asselen *et al.*, 2018). The lowest loss on ignition was observed at A2 site with a mean value of 87%. In this study, A2 site appears to be the oldest among all and have been in operation for oil palm cultivation for 34 years, when compared to A1 (15 years) and A3 (27 years), indicating that the peat in A2 site was severely oxidised due to the period of drainage. Although peat in A3 site was burned, the loss on ignition value was comparable with A1 site. The negligible of ash on peat surface is probably due to water movement and washed by rainfall. However, according to Hooijer *et al.*, (2012), the function of peat particle in post-fire occurrence to ash movement is limited and subjected to further study. Furthermore, the pH value was significantly higher in the UC microsite, which refers to an area rich in fertiliser and liming (Anuar *et al.*, 2008). Thus, higher pH could be associated with the level of mineralisation (Dariah *et al.*, 2014). Overall, the mean values of bulk density, loss on ignition, specific density, total porosity, volumetric water content, gravimetric water content, water-filled pores space, and pH are 0.176 g cm⁻³, 91.67%, 1.70 g cm⁻³, 89.04%, 41.8%, 266.3%, 46.57%, and 3.57, which are in line with those reported by Firdaus *et al.* (2011, 2012), Könönen *et al.* (2015), Matysek *et al.* (2018), Melling *et al.* (2005a), and Tonks *et al.* (2017) across various OP ages on tropical peatland.

Carbon emissions variation in oil palm plantation microsites

The CO₂ emission was varied between microsites (Figure 3). The highest emission at UC had been expected, being both a combination of AR and HR. However, the remaining sites exhibited interesting trends with fronds pile of decomposed stacked biomass (such as FP), as they resulted in lower emission than the UC site, but HP and FF were not clearly different. Despite FP having no understory biomass due to covered peat surface, poor environment to initiate plant growth is expected (Chalker-Scott, 2007). The stacked fronds may serve as organic mulches that support physical protection and increase water infiltration from the direct

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contact of above ground water (e.g. rainfall) (Mancinelli *et al.*, 2015). Rainfall is linked to momentary CO₂ emission, thus providing an adequate condition for microbial activity (Wakhid *et al.*, 2017). Higher CO₂ emission due to rainfall physical contact is supported by the positive relationship with water-related proxies, such as volumetric water content, gravimetric water content, and water-filled pore space (Table 6). A positive correlation between CO₂ emission and pH value was also discovered (Table 6). This suggests that the relationship is due to incorporation of rainfall and nitrate-based fertiliser or liming, particularly observed at UC microsites. Although this association is in agreement with that reported by Ishikura *et al.* (2018), the relationship may inversely change due to seasonal variation as pH is diluted by heavy rainfall (Marwanto *et al.*, 2018). Higher pH leads to increase the solubility of organic matter in wet soils (Pschenyckyj *et al.*, 2019), which may increase the availability of labile C to microbes respiration and enhance CO₂ production (Ye *et al.*, 2012) beside acetate pooling. In contrast, no significant variance was observed between OP ages and microsites on CH₄ emission. Similarly, a positive association between CH₄ emission and pH value (Table 6) was found. As discussed, higher pH value was obtained due to fertiliser or liming that potentially increased fermentative activity and thus availability of acetate and dehydrogen that subsequently increase methanogenic substrates that responsible for CH₄ production (Ye *et al.*, 2012). Overall, the cumulative of CO₂ and CH₄ among oil palm ages was from 453 to 1529 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ and from -61 to 406 µg CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹, which shared similar ranges with that reported by Melling *et al.*, (2005a, 2005b) in OP at Sarawak, Malaysia from 168 to 1228 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ and -43.7 to 5.6 µg CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹, respectively.

Microsites attribute to emission factor on oil palm plantation

As mentioned, FP microsite exhibited lower CO₂ emission, when compared to UC. The FP microsite is free from aboveground plant, which represents solely HR signature. The fact that UC is therefore higher than FP, is influenced by rainfall event or HR and AR; suggesting implications to emission from the activities associated with FP practise in plantation management. The reduced C emission from FP microsite demands further investigation in order to decipher the C balance related to organic matter contribution and rainfall physical protection from the reduced C loss from SR. Nonetheless, it has useful implications for optimised management of peat plantations, as discussed later in the next section, within the context of carbon balance by the fronds-stacking practice. The contribution of HR was compared using HP, FP, and FF to gain more insight on the wide range of AR/SR%. The AR was estimated by subtracting HR candidates (HP, FP, and FF microsities) from SR (UC microsite) and presented in AR/SR% (Table 7). Based on the results presented, AR/SR% refers to variation using HR candidates that ranged from 38% to 16% for all land usages. The highest value was calculated at the youngest OP (A1) and within the FP microsite (63%). This signified that the microsite had the lowest HR value that reflected undisturbed area of fronds piles and decomposed biomass, as mentioned earlier. On the contrary, the lowest AR/SR% value was recorded at A2 within HP microsite (9%). The HP areas were almost free from plants root due to active management practices, except for Bryophyte spp. such as mosses and other non-vascular plants. The impact from rainfall, owing to unprotected area, could add a major setting to higher HR value that indicated severely dry and oxidise site, hence the potential to generate immediate response to the pulse emission in the form of CO₂ (Fraser *et al.*, 2016; Ishikura *et al.*, 2017). Overall, the estimation of average AR/SR% using all microsities was 29% and fell within the range reported by Dariah *et al.*, (2014), and Melling *et al.*, (2013), of which 58% to 25%. The essential functions from each microsite for AR/SR% estimation is significant to gain more insight on the tropical peat status, instead of focusing on the best approach to quantify the value of HR through estimation of AR/SR%. This is because; the heterogeneity traits within microsities in terms of carbon cycle may alter the HR value, which is likely affected by the management practices.

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Table 7 Soil autotrophic estimation partitioning using under canopy (UC) microsite as the total soil respiration, while harvesting path (HP), frond pile (FP), and far from palm (FF) microsities as heterotrophic respiration from various land uses in oil palm plantation.

Age	Estimation of AR/SR% using respective microsities as HR candidate		
	HP	FP	FF
A1	24	63	37
A2	9	38	32
A3	15	12	30
Average	16	38	33

The variability of microsities from OP was employed to determine EF. Presently, the estimation of EF from OP on drained peatland seems to have vast uncertainties (EPA, 2014), and a wide range of default values from 40 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (IPCC, 2010) to 95 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (EPA, 2014). In this study, the EF from OP was 87 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and closer to the default value proposed by EPA (2014). It was expected as microsite-based calculation in this study involving the overall SR entities (AR, HR, and both as SR), wide range of water table levels, and emission pulse during wet season, when compared to IPCC 2010, which had been based solely on HR (Drösler *et al.*, 2014; Melling *et al.*, 2005). Nonetheless, the particular interest is towards active areas described by microsities (Table 2). The results revealed variances at HP, UC, FP, and FF microsities with 17%, 35%, 72%, and 5%, respectively (Figure 4). The highest difference was obtained for FP because it involved only a fraction of the entire microsities, when compared to the rest. Here, several strategies have been proposed to reduce EF from OP on drained tropical peatland using SAC. The first approach is to reduce the number of palms. As the SAC had been based on 160 palms per hectare, limiting up to 143 palms per hectare based on 9.0 m x 9.0 m x 9.0 m planting density may enhance the coefficients of FF and HP microsities, while decreasing FP and UC. In explaining the reduction, UC microsite was used due to its greatest CO₂ emission, in comparison to the others. From the calculations, EF decreased by 11% from 157 to 140 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. This reduction is attributable to the entire entities of SR (AR and HR) in UC, where the SAC factor decreased from 0.452 to 0.404. The second approach is through conversion of FF and HP microsities to FP, whereby FP in this study recorded the lowest CO₂ emission, when compared to other microsities. Hence, if FF, HP or both microsities are converted to FP, reduction of EFs by 1%, 5%, and 6% can be estimated. The calculation using SAC to estimate EF is equitable and represents the entire peat respiration entities (AR, HR or both as total SR) and pulse emission exclusive to OP on drained tropical peatland. Consideration of these microsities with area surface correction is integral and allows one to accurately estimate the amount of gas emission. Nevertheless, as the estimation from 35 to 157 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and indeed within to the default value proposed by EPA and IPCC (Hooijer *et al.*, 2012) and (Drösler *et al.*, 2014; Melling *et al.*, 2005a), with two sampling cycles may be insufficient to provide a holistic approach for the overall estimation in light of geographical area, pulse emission, type of peat, peat depth, and water table level (EPA, 2014). Therefore, further measurement in long term is required.

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Figure 4 CO₂ emissions from study sites with purposed default emissions factor. Dash line represents EPA (2014) purposed default emission factor that of 95 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, while solid line represents IPCC (2011) purposed default emission factor that of 40 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.

CONCLUSION

The hypothesis in this work probed into the intensity level of compaction based on bulk density value, mainly because OP management seems to remain ambiguous. Nevertheless, bulk density in this study is associated to peat maturity, which reflects periodical drainage by distinct of establishment OP ages. The heterogeneity of peat quality may lead to a wide range of carbon emissions. In fact, CO₂ emission rates have been linked with volumetric water content, gravimetric water content, water-filled pore space, and pH value. Meanwhile, CH₄ emission rates have been related to pH value. In line with this, the management practices on decayed frond stack at FP microsite offer physical protection and increase water infiltration from raindrops that potentially minimise CO₂ pulse emission. This provides the interim key to information for mitigation measures in reducing carbon emission from matured OP, for example, by using the SAC as proposed in this work. More importantly, future study related to artificial compaction by human-induction in controlled environment is necessary to further comprehend the mechanism behind artificial compaction on the impact of physicochemical properties and carbon gas emission from peat surface. Unfortunately, approach to induce controlled artificial compaction in field for tropical peatland is presently unavailable.

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Appendices List

Appendix A Animal tracks that observed at harvesting path in oil palm plantation, Sepang, South Selangor.

Appendix B Gas emissions were sampled at microsites within oil palm plantation using fabricated dynamic closed-chamber as shows in the sub-figure.

Appendix C The aboveground plant biomass in FF microsite area form a thick root mats like structure